

PLASTIC FLOW RULE OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES

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Abstract

Under certain operating conditions, composite materials may exhibit plastic flow properties, instead of the more common elastic deformation and brittle failures. Composite turbine blade operating under high temperature and composite armor subjected to high pressure impact are two examples where plastic flow may occur. In this paper, a plastic flow rule is derived for laminated media.

The proposed flow rule is based on a three-dimensional lamination theory, which produces an effective elastic stress-strain relation (1), and also gives an anisotropic yield condition for the composite (2). By considering isotropic layers that follow Prantle-Reuss flow rule (or any other classical ones), an anisotropic plastic stress-strain relation can be obtained for the equivalent composite medium.

The present flow rule differs greatly from that proposed by Hill (3). Hill's flow rule is a simple extension of his anisotropic yield condition, and has only one new constant in addition to the yield constants, and the symmetry of the flow rule cannot be different from that of yielding. The proposed flow rule has the following features: It can accommodate material flow constants in addition to yield constants; the symmetry of plastic flow (orthotropic, transversely isotropy, etc.) may be different from that of yielding; may be applied to both deformation theory, or incremental

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theory; all material properties (yield constants and flow constants) are tensors, therefore are easy to be transformed into other coordinates and to show symmetry.

Example numerical problems with different metal layered composites are calculated and discussed.

Introduction

Under certain operating conditions, composite materials may exhibit plastic flow properties, instead of the more common elastic deformation and brittle failures. Composite turbine blade operating under high temperature and composite armor subjected to high pressure impact are two examples where plastic flow may occur. In this paper, a plastic flow rule is derived for laminated media.

The proposed flow rule is based on a three-dimensional lamination theory, which produces an effective elastic stress strain relation (1), and also gives an anisotropic yield condition for the composite (2). By considering isotropic layers that follow Prantle-Reuss flow rule, an anisotropic plastic stress-strain relation can be obtained for the equivalent composite medium.

The plastic flow rule derived here for laminated medium may also be considered as the general form of plastic flow rule for homogeneous but anisotropic materials. If the thickness of the layers of a laminated medium decreases and the number of layer increases, then as a limit, we will have a homogeneous anisotropic medium. There are certain advantages in deriving the general forms of anisotropic properties as a limit of layered material. For instance, Ref. (2) shows that by using the laminate approach, and the criterion proposed by Tsai and Wu (3) is a direct extension of von Mises yield condition for isotropic medium. In the present paper, it will be shown that anisotropic flow rules are governed by tensor quantities, the plastic compliance tensor, which is a set of material property in addition to the yield constants; the symmetry of plastic flow may be different from that of yielding. Also, anisotropic material may yield and undergo plastic flow when subjected to pure hydrostatic loading.

After a layer in an n-layer laminate begins to yield, a redistribution of stress in each layer will occur, and the yielded layer behaves plastically, while the other layers remain elastic. The overall composite will have a new set of stress strain relations. Also, after each additional yielded layer, a new set of relations is formed.

Only limited numbers of plastic flow rules for anisotropic material have appeared in the literature. We shall discuss those proposed by Hill (4), Dorn (5), and Fisher (6).

In 1948, Hill extended the plastic potential theory for isotropic medium to that for anisotropic medium. He obtained a set of incremental plastic stress-strain relation of the form

$$d\epsilon_1^P = d\lambda [H(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2) + G(\sigma_1 - \sigma_3)]$$

where $d\epsilon_1^P$ is a component of the incremental plastic strain in contracted notation, H and G are two of the six yield constants, $d\lambda$ is a scalar function describing the hardening of the material, and σ_i are the current stresses. Note that Hill's flow rule is independent of the hydrostatic component of the stress, or plastically incompressible, a concept carried over from isotropic flow rule. Also, his anisotropy in plastic flow depends solely on the six yield constants: $d\lambda$ is the only function describing the extent of plastic flow. Both his yield condition and his plastic flow rule are not governed by tensor quantities.

In 1956, Hu (7) modified Hill's flow rule and introduced an expression for $d\lambda$ that was in terms of the effective stress and effective strain.

Dorn presented a general form of anisotropic flow rule, where he recognized 36 independent constants, and demonstrated the transformation of his plasticity coefficients with coordinate rotation in the two-dimensional case. His flow rule is of the form

$$\dot{\epsilon}_i^P = \dot{A}_{ij} \sigma_j$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}_i^P$ are the instantaneous plastic strain rates, σ_j are the stresses, and \dot{A}_{ij} are defined as the coefficients of plasticity. He also proposed that in general \dot{A}_{ij} were not constant; they depend on the history of flow and deformation. However, for some metals, the ratio of \dot{A}_{ij} remained constant, and he defined this case by a set of coefficient of constant anisotropy. He also introduced the expression

$$\dot{A}_{ij} = (\dot{\epsilon}^P / \bar{\sigma}) \alpha_{ij}$$

where α_{ij} are the coefficients of constant anisotropy, $\dot{\epsilon}^P$ is the effective plastic strain rate, and $\bar{\sigma}$ is the effective stress.

Fisher (6) used the distortion energy theory to formulate a set of anisotropic plastic flow equations. He recognized that there is a set of coefficients relating the plastic strain increments with stresses. However, he limited the formulation for a special case, that is material coordinate is coincided with the principal stress coordinate. Thus, his coefficients are not completely defined for all six stress components and they cannot be

considered as tensor quantity.

Plastic Stress Strain Relations

We shall limit our discussion to laminates of isotropic layers that follows von Mises yield condition and Hencky type total deformation plastic flow rule. The method used here can be applied easily to anisotropic layers, and other types of plastic stress-strain relations, as will be discussed later.

Consider a layered medium composed of n isotropic materials arranged in a repeating fashion. A representative element of the layered medium referred to the x_1, x_2, x_3 coordinate system is shown in Fig. 1. We shall consider this element to be small in relation to the overall dimension of the structure, and each layer is thin, so that the stress and strain fields in each layer within the element are uniform. It follows from the conditions of continuity of stress and displacement at the layer interfaces, i.e. the layers remain bonded and in equilibrium, that

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_i &= \sigma_i^k, & i = 1, 2, 6; & k = 1, 2 \dots n \\ \epsilon_i &= \sigma_i^k, & i = 3, 4, 5 & k = 1, 2 \dots n \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_i and σ_i are the strain and stress of the equivalent homogeneous element, or the overall composite element, superscript k refers to the k^{th} layer, and the contracted notation is used here and throughout this paper. The remaining stresses and strains of the element, those which may be discontinuous at the interfaces, are averaged according to volume, or

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_i &= \sum_{k=1}^n V^k \sigma_i^k, & i = 1, 2, 6 \\ \epsilon_i &= \sum_{k=1}^n V^k \epsilon_i^k, & i = 3, 4, 5 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where V^k is the volume fraction of layer k . These averaged quantities are also the "apparent" values which can be obtained directly from the definitions of stress and strain of the element. For instance, the total elongation of the element in x_3 direction divided by dx_3 is exactly the average given by (2).

It is convenient to write both elastic and plastic stress strain relations in terms of total stress and strain, instead of deviators, or

$$\epsilon_i^k = (S_{ij}^k + \psi_{ij}^k) \sigma_j^k, \quad \begin{matrix} i = 1, 2 \dots 6 \\ k = 1, 2 \dots n \end{matrix} \quad (3)$$

where S_{ij}^k is the elastic compliance tensor, and ψ_{ij}^k may be considered as the plastic compliance tensor, which is in general a function of σ_j^k . The S_{ij}^k tensor is related to the engineering constants by

$$S_{ij}^k = \frac{1}{E^k} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\nu^k & -\nu^k & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & 1 & -\nu^k & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & E^k/G^k & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & E^k/G^k & 0 \\ \text{Symmetry} & & & & & E^k/G^k \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where E is Young's modulus, ν Poisson's ratio, and G the shear modulus.

Before specifying ψ_{ij}^k , we may observe that Eqs. (1), (2) and (3) constitute $12n + 6$ equations, which govern $12n + 12$ variables, namely, $\sigma_i^k, \epsilon_i^k, \sigma_i^k, \epsilon_i^k, i = 1$ to $6; k = 1$ to n . Solving these equations, we may obtain the relations

$$\epsilon_i = f_i(\sigma_j) \quad (5)$$

and

$$\sigma_i^k = g_i(\sigma_j) \quad (6)$$

Equations (5) are the stress-strain relation of the equivalent overall element, and Eqs. (6) relate the stresses in each layer to the stresses of the overall element. In general, due to the non-linear nature of the ψ_{ij}^k term, Eqs. (5) and (6) cannot be expressed in explicit form, numerical methods must be used to solve for them. Under certain conditions, however, explicit forms may be obtained, as will be shown below.

If each layer follows the von Mises yield criterion,

$$F_{ij}^k \sigma_i^k \sigma_j^k = 1, \quad i, j = 1, 2 \dots 6 \quad (7)$$

then, in terms of the overall stresses, the criterion for the yielding of the k^{th} layer is

$$F_{ij}^k \sigma_i \sigma_j = 1 \quad i, j = 1, 2 \dots 6 \quad (8)$$

where H_{ij}^k and F_{ij}^k are given in (2). Let us assume that after yielding, each layer follows the Henky's stress-strain relation (4), then ψ_{ij}^k in Eq. (3) becomes

$$\psi_{ij}^k = 0, \quad \text{if } \bar{\sigma}^k < X^k$$

$$\psi_{ij}^k = \frac{(\bar{\epsilon}^P)^k}{\bar{\sigma}^k} \Phi_{ij}, \quad \text{if } \bar{\sigma}^k \geq X^k \quad (9)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}^k$ is the effective stress, or

$$\bar{\sigma}^k = (1/\sqrt{2}) \{(\sigma_1^k - \sigma_2^k)^2 + (\sigma_2^k - \sigma_3^k)^2 + (\sigma_3^k - \sigma_1^k)^2$$

$$+ 6[(\sigma_4^k)^2 + (\sigma_5^k)^2 + (\sigma_6^k)^2]\}^{1/2} \quad (10)$$

$$= \sqrt{2} [\Phi_{ij} \sigma_i^k \sigma_j^k]^{1/2}$$

X^k is the yield stress in simple tension, $\bar{\epsilon}^P$ is the effective plastic strain, related to strain components in a similar manner as the effective stress, and Φ_{ij} is a fourth rank isotropic tensor, or

$$\Phi_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1/2 & -1/2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & 1 & -1/2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & 3 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & 3 & 0 \\ \text{Symmetry} & & & & & 3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

The relation between the effective stress and effective plastic strain may be obtained from a simple tension test (7), and will be assumed known. If a bilinear relation, as shown in Fig. 2, is used, then $\bar{\epsilon}^P$ is

$$\bar{\epsilon}^P = (\bar{\sigma} - X) \beta, \quad (12)$$

where $\beta = (E - \bar{E})/E\bar{E}$, and \bar{E} is the slope of the hardening part of the effective stress-strain curve. Thus, the complete stress-strain relation for the k^{th} layer, Eq. (3) can be expressed in the

following form,

$$\epsilon_i^k = [S_{ij}^k + \frac{3}{2} \frac{\bar{\sigma}^k - X^k}{\bar{\sigma}^k} \beta^k \phi_{ij}] \sigma_j^k \quad (13)$$

This relation is still nonlinear in σ_j^k , since $\bar{\sigma}^k$ is a function of σ_j^k ; in general explicit forms of Eqs. (5) and (6) cannot be obtained. However, under proportional loading condition, ratios of $\sigma_i^k/\bar{\sigma}^k$ are constant, and σ_i^k can be expressed as linear functions of σ_j^k within the loading range where a fixed number of layers have yielded. Therefore

$$(\sigma_j^k / \bar{\sigma}^k) = \omega_j^k \quad (14)$$

where ω_j^k is a constant vector. In other words, within the range when one (or any number of) layer is in the plastic state, every layer is in a state of proportional loading with respect to the stress in that layer, σ_i^k . With Eq. (14), Eq. (13) may be written as

$$\epsilon_i^k = [S_{ij}^k + \frac{3}{2} \beta^k \phi_{ij}] \sigma_j^k - \frac{3}{2} X^k \beta^k \phi_{ij} \omega_j^k \quad (15)$$

This can be represented in a general form as

$$\epsilon_i^k = S'_{ij}{}^k \sigma_j^k + \epsilon_i'^k \quad (16)$$

where

$$S'_{ij}{}^k = S_{ij}^k + (3/2) \beta^k \phi_{ij}$$

$$\epsilon_i'^k = -(3/2) X^k \beta^k \phi_{ij} \omega_j^k$$

Now, Eqs. (1), (2) and (16) are all linear, and can be solved explicitly. The overall stress strain relations, (5), can be expressed as

$$\epsilon_i = S'_{ij} \sigma_j + \epsilon_i'$$

where

$$S'_{ij} = [\sum_{k=1}^n v^k (S'_{ij}{}^k)^{-1}]^{-1}, \quad i, j = 1, 2, 6$$

$$S_{ij} = \left[\sum_{k=1}^n v^k (S'_{im})^{-1} \right]^{-1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^n v^k (S'_{mn})^{-1} S'_{nj} \right], \quad i, m, n = 1, 2, 6; \\ j = 3, 4, 5$$

$$S_{ij} = \left[\sum_{k=1}^n v^k S'_{im} (S'_{mn})^{-1} \right] \left[\sum_{k=1}^n v^k (S'_{nj})^{-1} \right]^{-1}, \quad i = 3, 4, 5; \\ j, m, n = 1, 2, 6$$

$$S_{ij} = \left[\sum_{k=1}^n v^k S'_{im} (S'_{mn})^{-1} \right] \left[\sum_{k=1}^n v^k (S'_{nr})^{-1} \right]^{-1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^n v^k (S'_{rq})^{-1} S'_{qj} \right] \\ + \sum_{k=1}^n v^k [S'_{ij} - S'_{im} (S'_{mn})^{-1} (S'_{nj})], \quad i, j = 3, 4, 5; \\ m, n, q, r = 1, 2, 6$$

and

$$\epsilon'_i = \left[\sum_{k=1}^n v^k (S'_{ij})^{-1} \right]^{-1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^n v^k S'_{jm} \epsilon'_m \right], \quad i, j, m = 1, 2, 6$$

$$\epsilon'_i = \left[\sum_{k=1}^n v^k S'_{ij} (S'_{jm})^{-1} \right] \left[\sum_{k=1}^n v^k (S'_{mn})^{-1} \right]^{-1} \left[\sum_{k=1}^n v^k (S'_{nl}) \epsilon'_l \right]$$

$$+ \sum_{k=1}^n v^k \epsilon'_i - \sum_{k=1}^n v^k S'_{ij} (S'_{jm})^{-1} \epsilon'_m, \quad i = 3, 4, 5; \\ j, m, n, l = 1, 2, 6$$

Note that S'_{ij} depends on S'_{ij}^k only, and is independent of $\epsilon'_i{}^k$. The stresses in each layer may also be expressed in terms of the overall stresses,

$$\sigma_i^k = U_{ij}^k \sigma_j + \sigma_i^{rk} \quad (18)$$

where

$$U_{ij}^k = Q'_{im} S'_{mj}, \quad i, j, m = 1, 2, 6$$

$$U_{ij}^k = Q_{im}^k S_{mj}^k + Y_{ij}^k, \quad i, m = 1, 2, 6; j = 3, 4, 5$$

$$U_{ij}^k = \delta_{ij}, \quad i, j = 3, 4, 5$$

$$Q_{im}^k = C_{im}^k - C_{ij}^k \bar{C}_{jn}^k C_{nm}^k, \quad i, m = 1, 2, 6; j, n = 3, 4, 5$$

$$\bar{C}_{jn}^k = [C_{jn}^k]^{-1}, \quad j, n = 3, 4, 5$$

$$Y_{ij}^k = C_{im}^k \bar{C}_{mj}^k, \quad i = 1, 2, 6; j, m = 3, 4, 5$$

$$\sigma_i^{rk} = [S_{ij}^k]^{-1} (\epsilon_j^r - \epsilon_j^k), \quad i, j = 1, 2, 6$$

$$\sigma_i^{rk} = \delta_{ij} \sigma_j, \quad i, j = 3, 4, 5$$

and

$$C_{ij}^k = [S_{ij}^k]^{-1} \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, 6$$

When all layers are in the elastic range, $S_{ij}^k = S_{ij}^k$, and $\epsilon_i^k = 0$. As a result, $\epsilon_i^r = 0$ and S_{ij}^k in Eq. (17) can be shown to be identical to Eq. (10) of Ref. (1). The U_{ij}^k in Eq. (18) for elastic case is identical to that of (2).

The overall effective stress as a function of the overall effective strain may be calculated, a typical function in graphical form is shown in Fig. 3. It can be seen that each segment of this curve is a straight line, since Eqs. (17) are linear within each segment.

During unloading, we assume each layer follows the elastic slope of stress strain curve, with a constant plastic strain, or

$$\epsilon_i^k = S_{ij}^k \sigma_j^k + \epsilon_i^{pk} \quad (19)$$

where ϵ_i^{pk} are the plastic strain in the k^{th} layer, reached by the previous loading, and remain constant. The overall stress strain relation, (17) now reduces to

$$\epsilon_i = S_{ij} \sigma_j + \epsilon_i^p \quad (20)$$

where S_{ij} is the elastic compliance of the overall element, and ϵ_i^p is the overall plastic strain. The term ϵ_i^p represents the permanent set of the element upon complete unloading, $\sigma_i = 0$. The residual stress in each layer can be obtained from σ_i^r of (18), if ϵ_i^{pk} is used for ϵ_i^k .

The overall element exhibits transversely isotropic symmetry property, with 1,2 plane as the isotropic plane. It can be shown that S_{ij}^k , S_{ij}^k , and ϕ_{ij} are isotropic tensors, that is they are invariants under a coordinate transformation. Also, H_{ij}^k , F_{ij}^k , S_{ij} , and U_{ij}^k are all transversely isotropic tensors. Furthermore, ω_i^k defined by Eq. (14) are not known quantities beforehand when applying the present theory to a practical problem. However, they can be determined by solving Eq. (18) simultaneously. This has been done numerically for the following examples.

Numerical Examples

Two examples are presented to study the post-yielding behavior of laminated composites. In both examples, the response of the laminated composites due to different monotonic loading programs are examined. In the first example, a bilaminar composite of equal thickness of pure aluminum and copper is studied. In the second example, a composite of equal thickness of lead and copper is considered. The physical properties of aluminum, copper, and lead that are used in our calculation are listed in Table I. A bilinear effective stress, effective strain relation is assumed, with slopes E and \bar{E} . The yield stress and ultimate strength in simple tension are given as X and σ_{ult} , respectively.

Three states of stress that are applied to the first composite are uniaxial, hydrostatic, and the state of $\sigma_3 = \sigma_2 = -(\sigma_1/2)$. Only hydrostatic state of stress is applied to the second composite. The curves of the effective stress as a function of effective strain of the overall composite are shown in Figures 4 to 6. These curves are made up on linear segments. As discussed before, for bilinear layers, if there are n layers, there will be $n + 1$ linear segments, provided all layers will yield before the ultimate stress in any layer is reached. In these Figures, the cross marks indicate the point where the ultimate stress in aluminum is reached.

Figure 7 shows the result of lead-copper composite. In this case of hydrostatic loading, the stress in lead reaches its ultimate stress before the stress in aluminum reaches its yield value. As can be seen from Table I, the ultimate stress in lead is lower than the yielding stress in copper. Under this type of loading, the effective stress in lead is the same as that in aluminum; therefore, aluminum will not yield at all.

Concluding Remarks

In this paper, we limited our discussion to the case of proportion loading, which processes a linear stress-strain relation in the plastic range for each layer, thus the overall stress-strain relation of the composite can be solved explicitly. For the general case, the layer plastic stress-strain relation is non-linear, and the overall stress-strain relation can be obtained only by solving all the equations numerically. If the incremental theory is used for the layer plastic flow, the same procedure as in the present paper can be used, except that numerical method must be employed, and the overall plastic stress-strain relation will have a different type of symmetry for each loading step.

The plastic stress-strain relations derived here for layered media may be adopted to represent those for general anisotropic materials. Compared to the few existing anisotropic theories, the present one has the advantages that (1) all material properties (yield constants and plasticity constants) are tensor quantities, therefore, are easy to be transformed into other coordinates and to show symmetry; (2) the plastic stress-strain relations depend not only on yield constant, additional material properties are included. This makes it convenient to match any experimental data; (3) the general approach may be applied to either the deformation theory, or the incremental theory.

TABLE I

Physical Properties for Aluminum, Copper and Lead

	Pure Aluminum	Copper	Lead
E	10×10^6 psi	17.3×10^6 psi	2×10^6 psi
ν	0.33	0.35	0.43
\bar{E}	3.3×10^6 psi	6×10^6 psi	0.5×10^6 psi
t	0.5 in.	0.5 in.	0.5 in.
σ_y	3000 psi	10000 psi	2000 psi
σ_{ult}	16000 psi	32000 psi	3000 psi

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1. Typical n-Layered Medium.

2. A Typical Stress-Strain Curve for Bilinear Materials.

3. A Typical Stress-Strain Curve for Laminated Media.

4. Theoretical Uniaxial Stress-Strain Curve of a Al-Cu Laminated Composite.

5. Theoretical Stress-Strain Curve for Al-Cu Laminated Composites Subjected to Hydrostatic Stress.

6. Theoretical Stress-Strain Curve for Al-Cu Laminated Composites Subjected to $\sigma_2 = \sigma_3 = -(\sigma_1/2)$ Loading.

7. Theoretical Stress-Strain Curve for a Pb-Cu Laminated Composites Subjected to Hydrostatic Stress.